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J.W. RYDE.

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SCATTER INTENSITIES AND ATTENUATION DUE TO CLOUDS,
RAIN, HAIL, SAND AND DUSTSTORMS AT CENTIMETRE
WAVELENGTHS.

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The Report came to me from Peter Ryde, son of the author John W. Ryde and his wife Dorothy, who assisted him by performing much of the mathematical work: she was a first cousin of my father, and it was amongst her belongings when she died. The image quality is about the best that could be produced, given the age of the paper and its general condition, plus the fact that it was typed and printed by the wax stencil process in common use at the time.

Lex Haworth

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ECHO INTENSITIES AND ATTENUATION DUE TO CLOUDS,
RAIN, HAIL, SAND AND DUSTSTORMS AT CENTIMETRE
WAVELENGTHS.

This report gives a detailed computation of the ratio of echo intensities from clouds, rain, hail etc. to that from aircraft. The attenuation is also calculated, as well as the absolute values of the echo intensities, for a range of wavelengths from 1 to 100 cm.

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(1) SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS.

The general object of this investigation is to provide data by which the likelihood of trouble, due to echoes from rain and similar meteorological conditions, can be assessed for different wavelengths down to 1 cm. and also to determine the attenuation for point to point transmission. The well known Rayleigh theory of scattering is inadequate for this purpose and the present work is based on the general and exact theory of G.Mie.

In Section (2) the necessary expressions for the absolute echo intensity and also for the ratio of the echo intensity to that from an aircraft within the rain or cloud are determined.

In Section (3) the scattering function for a single drop is determined in terms of ten coefficients which are given in Appendix (1). These coefficients are themselves functions of the refractive index and absorption index of water for the particular wavelength considered; data regarding these indices are summarised in Section (4). Similarly, Sections (5) or (6) contain relevant meteorological data.

The next two sections describe the computation of the scattering coefficients. A standard object, namely a perfectly conducting sphere of about three and a half metres diameter, has been assumed throughout to take the place of the aircraft.

The results obtained are summarised in Section (9) and are shown graphically in Figure (3). From this Figure can be read off the wavelength λ at which, for a given distance and beam divergence, the echo intensities from cloud and aircraft are equal or are in some given proportion.

A summary of the conditions under which appreciable echoes may be expected to occur is given on p.16, to which reference should be made. Recorded observations of cloud echoes are discussed in Section (10) and are shown to be in general agreement with the theory.

The case of hailstorms is treated in Sections (11) and (12) and the results are shown diagrammatically in Figure (5). The theory is again found to be in accord with observation. Briefly, it is expected that, for $\lambda = 3$ cm., appreciable echoes will be produced by clouds containing hailstones as small as 0.1 cm. in diameter, while for $\lambda = 10$ cm., the diameter needs to be 0.3 cm. and for $\lambda = 50$ cm. large hailstones of some 1.7 cm. are necessary.

Echo intensities from tropical sand and dust storms are considered in Section (13) and the minimum mass of sand or dust, per cubic metre of air, that is necessary to produce an appreciable echo is given in Table (+) on p. 24.

The effect on the echo intensity of attenuation by the drops within the cloud is next considered. It is shown on p.27, that below about $\lambda = 3$ cm. and more particularly at $\lambda = 1$ cm. obliteration and masking effects may occur. The beam might be pointed in the direction of a severe storm cloud containing large drops and behind which there were aircraft and then, not only would no echoes be observed from the aircraft, but there would be little or no indication that the cloud was there.

A table showing, in a number of instances, the ratio of the echo peak intensity for $\lambda = 3$ cm. to that for $\lambda = 10$ cm. and also the ratio for $\lambda = 1$ cm. to that for $\lambda = 3$ cm. is given on p. 28.

The attenuation* under conditions of point to point transmission is considered in detail in Section (16), p. 29.

It is shown that only for very small droplets can it be said that the attenuation depends on the total mass of liquid water present, irrespective of the drop diameter. The fact is that, as shown in Figure (8), for a given mass of water, in the form of droplets more than 0.05 cm. in diameter, the attenuation is much greater if they are large than if they are small. The results are summarised in Figure (7) for small droplets and Figure (9) for large ones. A scale of the db. loss per Km. will be found on the right hand side in each case.

In interpreting the results given in the text and in the Figures, the considerations discussed in Section (5) must be borne in mind. In particular, it should be noted that the curves on the Figures and data in the Tables are given primarily in terms of reference numbers corresponding with the particular values of particle diameter D and concentration N given in Table (2). p.11. The descriptions "Very Heavy Rain" etc. are given only as a general guide; it is the values of

* Previous computations of attenuation by water droplets have been given by Stratton and Fränz. Stratton assumes zero absorption index and so obtains values which are far too low, while Fränz considers only fine droplets for which the attenuation, at short wavelengths, is very small compared with that for large rain drops,

N and D in the cloud itself which are fundamental.

Another point which should be emphasised is that, since the attenuation depends greatly on the assumed absorption index of water, the accuracy of the attenuation constants derived is dependent on the accuracy of the published values for the absorption index.

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(2) EXPRESSIONS FOR THE ECHO INTENSITIES.

Let I_1 be the intensity of the outgoing polarised radiation at unit distance from the transmitter which, for simplicity, will be considered as a point source emitting a conical beam having a semi-angle θ . Suppose further that the beam falls on a cloud at a distance r and that the cloud fills the cross section of the beam at that distance.

We require to determine the ratio of the echo intensities from the cloud and from an aircraft within it.

The intensity, at the transmitter, of radiation back scattered from a single droplet at distance r will be,

$$\frac{I_1}{r^2} \cdot \frac{B_1}{r^2} \quad (1)$$

where B_1 is a scattering function depending on the wavelength, the nature of the droplet and its diameter.

If there are N droplets per unit volume in the cloud, the echo intensity from those droplets lying in that part of a spherical shell of thickness dr (centred at the source) which is intersected by the beam will be,

$$\frac{I_1 N B_1}{r^4} \cdot 2\pi r^2 (1 - \cos \theta) dr \quad (2)$$

The assumption that the intensity will be proportional to N is valid, provided the distance between the droplets is large compared with their diameter. This is true for all the cases we shall consider below.

Integrating (2) over the pulse length h we find that, at the instant when the centre of the pulse is at a distance r , the echo intensity I_2 at the source is given by

$$I_2 = I_1 N B_1 \cdot 2\pi (1 - \cos \theta) \int_{r_1}^{r_2} \frac{dr}{r^2}$$

where

$$r_1 = r - \frac{h}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad r_2 = r + \frac{h}{2}$$

so that,

$$I_2 = \frac{I_1 N B_1 \cdot 2\pi (1 - \cos \theta)}{\left(\frac{r^2}{h} - \frac{h}{4}\right)} \quad (3) \quad \text{As/}$$

As will appear later it will be convenient to write

$$B_1 = \left(\frac{\lambda}{2\pi}\right)^2 f_0(\alpha, m) \quad (4)$$

where λ is the wavelength of the incident polarised radiation, while $f_0(\alpha, m)$ is a function depending on

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{\pi D_1}{\lambda} \quad (5)$$

in which D_1 is the diameter of the droplets, and m which is a function (discussed later) of the refractive index and the absorption index of the material composing the drops.

It will also be convenient to take N as the number of droplets per cm^3 , λ and D in cm ., but the distances r and k in Km . Then (3) becomes

$$I_r = I_1 \lambda^2 N f_0(\alpha, m) \frac{(1 - \cos \theta) 10^5}{2\pi \left(\frac{r^2}{k} - \frac{k}{4}\right)} \quad (6)$$

If we now suppose the aircraft to be replaced by an equivalent metal sphere of diameter D_2 then, corresponding to (4) and (5) we shall have,

$$B_2 = \left(\frac{\lambda}{2\pi}\right)^2 F_0(\alpha_2) \quad (7)$$

and

$$\alpha_2 = \frac{\pi D_2}{\lambda} \quad (8)$$

The ratio k of the echo intensities, from the cloud and from the metal sphere respectively, will then be given by,

$$k = \frac{I_r}{I_{\text{sphere}}} = \frac{N f_0(\alpha, m)}{F_0(\alpha_2)} \left\{ \frac{r^4}{\frac{r^2}{k} - \frac{k}{4}} \right\} 2\pi (1 - \cos \theta) 10^5 \quad (9)$$

If r is much greater than k and if the divergence Δ of the beam is not more than say 40° this expression reduces to the simple form,

$$k = 2.4 \cdot 10^{11} k r^2 \Delta^2 \frac{N f_0(\alpha, m)}{F_0(\alpha_2)} \quad (10)$$

where/

where h and r are in Km, Δ is in degrees and N is the number of droplets per cm^3 .

Similarly (6) giving the intensity of the radiation back scattered to the source, relative to the outgoing intensity at a distance of 1 Km. becomes,

$$\frac{I_2}{I_1} = 0.605 \frac{R \Delta^2}{r^2} \cdot \lambda^2 N f_0(\alpha, m) \quad (11)$$

It may be noted that the echo trace from the cloud will appear in the form of exaggerated shot noise, since the scattering particles are randomly distributed.

(3) THE SCATTERING FUNCTIONS $f_0(\alpha, m)$ and $f_\pi(\alpha, m)$.

The problem of the scattering of radiation by spheres has received considerable attention in the past. Some of these theoretical investigations are more particularly directed to special cases, such as perfect dielectrics or perfectly conducting spheres, but the treatment most suitable for our present purposes is the general and exact electromagnetic theory of G.Mie.(1).

According to this, the scattering function for the radiation back scattered in a direction towards the source ($\gamma = 0$) takes the form,

$$f_0(\alpha, m) = \frac{1}{4} \left| \sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} (a_\nu + p_\nu) \right|^2 \quad (12)$$

in which a_ν and p_ν are complex coefficients related to the amplitudes of the ν^{th} electric and magnetic partial waves respectively.

Similarly, the intensity scattered in any other direction can be found from a more complicated expression depending on the coefficients a_ν and p_ν .

For example, the next simplest case is that for the intensity scattered in the forward direction ($\gamma = 180^\circ$) and then,

$$f_\pi(\alpha, m) = \frac{1}{4} \left| \sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{\nu+1} (a_\nu - p_\nu) \right|^2 \quad (12b)$$

Mie's expressions for a_ν and p_ν are very complicated, but they can be put in a more convenient form by expressing them in terms of Bessel Functions of half integral order. Thus, let

(13)/

(1) G.Mie, Ann.d.Phys. 25.p.377,1908.

$$S_\nu(x) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}\pi x} J_{\nu+\frac{1}{2}}(x) \quad (13)$$

$$C_\nu(x) = (-1)^\nu \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}\pi x} J_{-\nu-\frac{1}{2}}(x)$$

and

$$E_\nu(x) = C_\nu(x) - i S_\nu(x)$$

Also let $S'_\nu(x)$, $C'_\nu(x)$ and $E'_\nu(x)$ be the corresponding first derivatives, then Mie's expressions become,

$$a_\nu = (-1)^\nu (2\nu+1) \frac{S'_\nu(\alpha)}{E'_\nu(\alpha)} \cdot \frac{\frac{S_\nu(\alpha)}{S'_\nu(\alpha)} - m \frac{S_\nu(m\alpha)}{S'_\nu(m\alpha)}}{\frac{E_\nu(\alpha)}{E'_\nu(\alpha)} - m \frac{S_\nu(m\alpha)}{S'_\nu(m\alpha)}} \quad (14)$$

$$p_\nu = (-1)^{\nu+1} (2\nu+1) \frac{S'_\nu(\alpha)}{E'_\nu(\alpha)} \cdot \frac{\frac{S_\nu(\alpha)}{S'_\nu(\alpha)} - \frac{1}{m} \frac{S_\nu(m\alpha)}{S'_\nu(m\alpha)}}{\frac{E_\nu(\alpha)}{E'_\nu(\alpha)} - \frac{1}{m} \frac{S_\nu(m\alpha)}{S'_\nu(m\alpha)}} \quad (15)$$

in which

$$\alpha = \frac{\pi n_0 D}{\lambda}$$

(16)

where/

where D is the diameter of the sphere, n_0 the refractive index of the medium surrounding the sphere and λ is the wavelength in vacuo. In the present applications n_0 can be taken as unity.

In the case of a dielectric sphere of a material having a zero absorption coefficient for the wavelength in question, m in the above expressions may be identified with the ratio of the ordinary refractive index n of the material, to n_0 the refractive index of the medium in which the sphere is surrounded; both indices of refraction must of course be those for the given wavelength.

If, however, the absorption index χ is not zero, we must write,

$$m = n (1 - i\chi) \quad (17)$$

so that, in general, m is a complex quantity.

If, further, the sphere is infinitely conducting, which may be assumed to be the case for metals at radio wavelengths, (although not for visible light for example) we must put

$$m = -i\infty \quad (19)$$

and (14) and (15) may be somewhat simplified.

It may be noted that the attenuation through a homogeneous layer x cm. in thickness and of a material similar to that of the sphere is given by

$$I = I_0 e^{-\frac{4\pi n \chi}{\lambda} x} \quad (18)$$

where λ is the wavelength in vacuo.

Existing tables of the functions (13) are of limited extent and, moreover, have not been computed for complex arguments. In order, therefore, to deal with complex values of m the following procedure was adopted.

Expressions (14) and (15) were separated into real and imaginary parts and then, by means of the known series for the S_ν and C_ν functions, expansions for a_ν and p_ν in powers of α were obtained, retaining powers of α up to the ninth.

For real m , these expressions enable a_ν and p_ν to be readily computed for sphere diameters up to about one third of the wavelength. Beyond this, the expressions (13) to (15) must be used.

For complex m let us write

$$\begin{aligned}
 m &= n(1 - i\chi) \\
 \epsilon &= m^2 = g - ik
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{20}$$

where ϵ is the generalised dielectric constant.*

Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
 g &= n^2(1 - \chi^2) \\
 k &= 2n^2\chi
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{21}$$

The following expressions for n and χ in terms of g and k are sometimes useful.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \chi &= \left[1 + \left(\frac{g}{k} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{g}{k} \\
 2n^2 &= \frac{k}{\chi} = k \left[1 + \left(\frac{g}{k} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} + g
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{22}$$

It may also be noted that observational data are frequently given in terms of the phase angle Φ defined by

$$\tan \Phi = \frac{k}{g} = \frac{2\chi}{1 - \chi^2}
 \tag{23}$$

Substituting (20) into the above mentioned series for a_ν and p_ν and again separating into real and imaginary parts we obtain the expansions required. These are given below in Appendix (1). Here powers of α above the sixth have been neglected; this is legitimate for all the water droplet cases with which we shall be concerned in this report.

Substitution in (12) then gives the required expression for the scattering function in the form,

(25) /

* In dispersion theory, in place of (20) it is usual to write

$$\epsilon = \epsilon' - i\epsilon''
 \tag{24}$$

but primed letters are cumbersome to use in the complicated expressions we shall derive and for this reason g and k have been used in place of ϵ' and ϵ'' respectively. No confusion should arise between the k of this Section and that of Section (2) in which it is used for the pulse length.

$$f_0(\alpha, m) = \frac{\alpha^6}{4} \left[\left\{ q_1 + (q_2 - u_1 - w_1) \alpha^2 - q_3 \alpha^3 \right\}^2 + \left\{ r_1 + (r_2 - v_1 - w_2) \alpha^2 + r_3 \alpha^3 \right\}^2 \right] \quad (25)$$

in which the coefficients q_1, r_1 , etc. are the functions of g and h given in Appendix (1).

If the diameter of the particles is so small compared with the wavelength that the second and third terms in each of the two curled brackets can be neglected relatively to the first, then

$$\begin{aligned} f_0(\alpha, m) &\doteq \alpha^6 \frac{q_1^2 + r_1^2}{4} = \alpha^6 \frac{(g-1)^2 + h^2}{(g+2)^2 + h^2} \\ &= \alpha^6 \frac{(n^2-1)^2 + n^2 \chi^2 [2(n^2+1) + n^2 \chi^2]}{(n^2+2)^2 + n^2 \chi^2 [2(n^2-2) + n^2 \chi^2]} \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

If, further, the absorption index is zero we have,

$$\begin{aligned} f_0(\alpha, m) &\doteq \alpha^6 \left(\frac{n^2-1}{n^2+2} \right)^2 \\ (\chi=0) & \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Before proceeding with the numerical computation of the scattering function, we must first consider the values of g and h for water and then the meteorological data regarding the size and concentration of the water droplets in clouds and rain.

It/

It will be found that, for the shorter wavelengths below about 5 cm., the approximations (26) and (27) are not sufficiently accurate for drops as large as rain so that (25) must be used in general. For fogs, mists and drizzle, however, the approximate expressions are valid.

(4) VALUES OF n AND χ FOR WATER.

A review of the literature shows that for wavelengths down to about 10 cms. the refractive index of water is closely 8.9. As the wavelength decreases further, the refractive index falls rapidly and becomes 2.0 in the far infra red; subsequently it falls further to the value 1.33 in the visible spectrum. On the other hand, the absorption index χ first rises as the wavelength decreases and then passes through a well defined maximum in the neighbourhood of 2 cms.

Measurements in the region with which we are chiefly concerned, namely from 25 cm. down to 0.5 cm. have been carried out by Mobius (2), Tear (3) and Knerr (4). Additional information is given in the Handbuch der Physik (5) and by Esau and Buz. (6).

The data are plotted in Figures (1) and (4). In the first of these a few of the experimental points are shown and the abscissa covers the range of wavelengths in which we are chiefly interested. In Figure (4) the general trend of n and $n\chi$ is shown over a large range of wavelengths down to the near infra red. We shall have occasion to refer to these latter curves when the values for ice are considered.

The adopted values of n and $n\chi$ together with the corresponding values of g and h used in the following computations, are given in Table (1) below.

Table (1).

Adopted Values of n and $n\chi$ for water
at various wavelengths.

λ_{cm}	n	$n\chi$	$g = \epsilon'$	$h = \epsilon''$	Φ
1	5.8	1.4	31.68	16.24	27°
2	7.2	2.5	45.6	36.0	38.5
3	7.9	2.0	58.41	31.6	28.5
5	8.6	1.3	72.27	22.36	17
10	8.8	0.7	77.83	10.39	7.5
20	8.85	0.5	78.07	8.85	6.5
100	8.94	(0.27)	80.0	4.8	3.5

(5)/

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- (2) Mobius. Ann. d. Phys. 62. p. 293. 1920.
 (3) Tear, Phys. Rev. 21. p. 620. 1923.
 (4) Knerr, Phys. Rev. 52. p. 1054. 1937.
 (5) Handbuch der Physik. Vol. 15. p. 513.
 (6) A. Esau and G. Buz. Phys. Zeits. 38. p. 774. 1937.

(5) VALUES OF N AND D

We now need values of the drop diameter D and the number N of droplets per c.c. for various meteorological conditions. Data have been given by Humphreys (7) from which source the principal values in Table (2) have been derived.

Table (2).

Values of N and D

	Ref. No.	Rate of Precipitation. Inches per hour.	Typical Droplet Diameter D cm.	Typical Number per cm. ³ N	Mass of liquid water per cubic metre, grams.
Thunder storms & very heavy rain.	(1)	-	0.5	(1.4×10^{-4})	9.2
	(2)	4.0	0.3	3.8×10^{-4}	5.4
	(3)	1.6	0.21	3.8×10^{-4}	1.85
Heavy Rain.	(4)	0.6	0.15	4.7×10^{-4}	0.83
Moderate Rain	(5)	0.16	0.10	5.3×10^{-4}	0.28
Light Rain	(6)	0.04	0.045	2.9×10^{-3}	0.14
Drizzle	(7)	0.01	0.02	2.2×10^{-2}	0.093
Mist	(8)	0.002	0.01	1.05×10^{-1}	0.056
Stratus & Fine Weather	(9)	-	0.0033	120	2.39
Stratocummulus.					
Dense Sea Fog	(10)	-	0.001	1200	0.63
Fog	(11)	-	0.001	11.5	0.006

If the precipitation rate persists for some time, the conditions corresponding to reference numbers (2) and (3) are designated 'Cloudburst' and 'Excessive Rain' by meteorologists. Precipitation rates much in excess of 4 inches an hour may, however, occur at a given point on the ground for a short time during heavy thunderstorms. Reference number (1) corresponds to rain from the heaviest thunderstorm likely to be experienced. It should, however, be noted that much larger sphere diameters may occur in thunderstorms producing hail; this case will be considered later and until then it is to be understood that the drops are composed of pure water. It is hoped later to deal with the modifications produced when the water contains dissolved salts.

The values given in Table (2) are typical, but there may be a very considerable variation, particularly in the value of N for given D and this must be borne in mind. It must not be assumed that, for example, a given precipitation rate will closely correspond with the values of N and D tabulated.

Another/

(7) Humphreys, Physics of the Air, (1929).

Another point is that we are more interested in the conditions obtaining in the clouds themselves than in those near the ground, but most of the data concerning N and D refer to the latter case. Nevertheless, by working with the wide range of values given in Table (2) we shall be fairly sure of including the likely range of cloud conditions.

It is, of course, by no means necessary that rain should be observed to fall in order that drops of large diameter should occur, for even the largest drops may be kept suspended by the strong rising air currents in cumulus and cumulo-nimbus clouds and they may not be precipitated on the ground as rain for some time. Again, conditions sometimes occur when evaporation at the lower levels is so rapid that drops, starting to fall as rain, re-evaporate on the way down and disappear long before reaching the ground. It is thus by no means necessary for rain to be falling in order that echoes from clouds should be observed; all that is necessary is that the requisite values of N and D should obtain in the cloud itself.

At the top of a rain cloud the droplet size will be small and N large but, as we come down into the centre of the cloud the droplet size will increase. It would seem likely that, in thunderstorms, the concentration will be higher in the centre of the cloud than in the rain at ground level so that, although the cases corresponding to our reference numbers (1) and (2) are only occasionally met with near the ground, even higher concentrations may occur more frequently in the centres of thunderclouds.

The maximum size of rain drops possible is about 0.55 to 0.66 cm.; drops larger than this are unstable when falling through the air and, if formed, they would immediately break up into smaller ones. It follows that D will never be much larger than corresponds to our case (1) but, as mentioned above, the value of N in the heart of thunderclouds may exceed the figure tabulated for the concentration near the ground.

In mid-latitudes, the freezing point is reached, on the average, at a height of about 4 Km. Hence in those cumulo-nimbus clouds which extend appreciably above this level, the drops, which are kept suspended by the powerful rising air currents necessarily present in thunder clouds, quickly congeal and form hailstones. The diameter of these is naturally not restricted by instability and they may grow to a considerable size.*

(6) CLOUD HEIGHTS.

In the case of light and moderate rain, the base of the cloud from which it falls occurs, on the average, at a height of 0.6 Km. and the cloud layer may extend up to a height of 2.0 to 3.0 Km., above the earth's surface, although occasionally rain may fall from a cloud layer only 1 Km. thick. On the other hand, the cumulo-nimbus clouds producing/

* The largest hailstones on record were some 12 cm. in diameter, and weighed 2 lbs. or more. An up-draught of about 90 m/sec. would be necessary to support them; this would also be their terminal velocity. The terminal velocity of the largest rain drops 0.55 cm. in diameter is 8 m/sec. while that of moderate rain is about half this.

producing the heavier precipitation rates extend from 0.5 to 6 Km. and, especially, in the tropics, to even 10 Km. or more. The average value of the height of the top of these clouds in latitudes from 50° to 60° N is about 4 to 5 Km. and heavy rain drops or hail may be presumed to extend to roughly 75% or more of the total height. The base of these clouds is generally about 1 Km. above the surface of the ground.

Data on high lying cirrus type clouds, which are composed of ice particles or supercooled fine water droplets, will be given in a later section.

(7) THE COMPUTATION OF $N f_0(\alpha, m)$

We can now proceed to compute the factor $N f_0(\alpha, m)$ which occurs in (6) to (11). For the droplet sizes with which we are concerned, the convergence of the series (12) is rapid and we need only determine the partial wave coefficients a_1, a_2 and b_1 for which series, in the case of complex m , are given in Appendix (1).

Values of the logarithm of the scattering function,

$$4\pi^2 NB_1 = \lambda^2 N f_0(\alpha, m)$$

for use in (6) and (11), were computed from the accurate expression (25) and are shown, plotted against $\log \lambda$ in Figure (2) for the various meteorological conditions given in Table (2). From Figure (2) and equations (6) or (11) the back scattered intensity, relative to the intensity of the outgoing beam at a distance of 1 Km. from the source, may now be obtained immediately. It is of interest to see over what part of the diagram it is legitimate to replace (25) by much simpler approximate expressions.

First, when the droplets are very small compared with the wavelength and when the absorption index can be neglected we have by (27),

$$4\pi^2 NB_1 = \lambda^2 N f_0(\alpha, m) \sim N \pi^6 \frac{D^6}{\lambda^4} \left(\frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} \right)^2 \quad (28)$$

in conformity with the well known Rayleigh law for indefinitely small particles.

Second, if the droplets are very small, but the absorption index cannot be neglected, then by (26), for small values of α ,

$$\lambda^2 N f_0(\alpha, m) \sim N \pi^6 \frac{D^6}{\lambda^4} \frac{(n^2 - 1)^2 + n^2 \chi^2 [2(n^2 + 1) + n^2 \chi^2]}{(n^2 + 1)^2 + n^2 \chi^2 [2(n^2 - 1) + n^2 \chi^2]} \quad (28b)$$

It will be seen that, over the range of validity of these approximate expressions, the echo intensity varies as the sixth power of the droplet diameter and as the inverse fourth power of the wavelength, provided that n and $n\lambda$ are sensibly constant. Thus, for the smaller particles and longer wavelengths, the plots in Figure (2) are approximately straight lines. Actually, as the wavelength decreases it will be seen from Table (1) that, down to $\lambda = 2$ cm., as n falls, $n\lambda$ increases, and the changes to some extent compensate each other. The combined effect of these changes together with the increase of α will, however, be seen from Figure (2) to produce a reduction of the intensity when D/λ becomes greater than 0.03. This limit is shown by the dotted line; below this (28b) can be used, but above it the more accurate expression (25) must be employed.

(8) THE COMPUTATION OF $F_0(\alpha)$

We must now consider the values of the scattering function $F_0(\alpha_2)$ in (7) to (10), for a metal sphere equivalent to an aeroplane. The choice of diameter must, of necessity, be rough since an aircraft is a complicated structure. The most reasonable first approximation is to make the projected areas comparable. Assuming this area to be 10 square metres we accordingly find $D_2 = 356$ cm. for the "equivalent" diameter.

In this case the sphere diameter is much greater than λ and, even for a wavelength as large as one metre, the value of α is such that the convergence of the series (12) is slow and the computations become extremely laborious. It can, however, be shown that as α increases still further, the values of the function $F_0(\alpha)$ oscillate about a 'mean' value proportional to α^2 . A large number of values of $F_0(\alpha)$ were computed* by (14) and (15) for values of α up to about 10 and from these, together with the relation,

$$F_0(\alpha_2) \sim q\alpha^2 \quad (29)$$

where q is some constant. It can be shown that, over the range in which we are interested, the values of $F_0(\alpha_2)$ determined from,

$$F_0(\alpha_2) = 0.45\alpha_2^2 \quad (30)$$

are/

* It is intended to discuss these computations and the derivation of (30) in a subsequent report in which the scattering functions for spheres of water, ice, etc. which are large compared with the wavelength will be treated in a similar manner.

are not likely to be in error by as much as 50%. This degree of accuracy is ample for our purpose.

Remembering (7) and substituting (16) with $n_0 = 1$ for air, we obtain the relation,

$$4 \pi^2 B_2 = \lambda^2 \bar{V}_2(x_2) = 4.44 D_2^2 \quad (31)$$

From this, together with (10) we find,

$$\lambda^2 N f_0(x, m) = 1.86 \cdot 10^{-11} \frac{k D_2^2}{r^2 \Delta^2} \quad (32)$$

where it will be remembered that k is the ratio of the echo intensity from the cloud to that of the sphere.

Now, clearly, the sphere diameter equivalent to different aircraft will vary considerably, and, moreover, it will also vary for different aspects of the same aircraft. We shall therefore introduce a factor G to allow for this, remembering that $G = 1$ corresponds to a perfectly conducting sphere of diameter $D_2 = 356$ cm. Then, taking a pulse width of 0.5 Km., which roughly corresponds to 1.5 μ s., (32) becomes,

$$\lambda^2 N f_0(x, m) = 4.72 \cdot 10^{-6} \frac{k G^2}{r^2 \Delta^2} \quad (33)$$

This expression is amply accurate for our purpose provided that r is greater than about 1.5 Km. and the beam divergence Δ is less than 40°.

(9) THE RATIO OF ECHO INTENSITIES SHOWN DIAGRAMMATICALLY.

It will be remembered that we have already computed the left hand side of (33) for different wavelengths and various meteorological conditions. It follows that, for any given values of r , Δ and G we can find the particular meteorological condition which will produce an assigned ratio k of echo intensities for any wavelength. This is most easily done by utilising (33) to replot Figure (2) so that the ordinates are expressed directly in terms of $\log_{10}(k G^2 / r^2 \Delta^2)$; we have only to add 5.33 to the ordinate scale. The resulting plots are shown in Figure (3).

As an illustration of the use of this Figure let us fix the ratio k as 0.1, then, for a constant value of the product $r \Delta = 16$ that is, for say,

$$\Delta = 2^\circ \quad r = 8 \text{ Km.}$$

$$\text{or } \Delta = 10^\circ \quad r = 1.6 \text{ Km.} \approx 1 \text{ mile etc.}$$

We have for $G = 1$

$$\log_{10} \frac{k G^2}{r^2 \Delta^2} = 4.6$$

A horizontal line, shown dashed, in Figure (3) has been drawn for this value of the ordinate. For the above conditions we can now read off the reference numbers corresponding to the meteorological conditions which, for different wavelengths, will give a ratio of echo intensities $k = 0.1$.

Similarly, the full line drawn through the ordinate 3.55 is for the same conditions with $G = 3$. We shall see later that $G = 3$ may at times correspond better with observation than $G = 1$.

We now see immediately that, for the above condition $r \Delta = 16$, if $\lambda > 30$ cm., the echo intensities from even the heaviest storms will be inappreciable compared with that from an aircraft.

for $\lambda = 10$ cm., only in the case of heavy thunderstorms will the ratio k of the echo intensities from storm and aircraft be likely to attain 0.1. The effects of light rain, drizzle, mist and fog will be quite inappreciable.

for $\lambda = 3$ cm. the ratio k may attain 0.1 for moderate rain while the echo from a heavy storm may obliterate that from an aircraft within it. Drizzle, mist and fog will produce inappreciable effects.

for $\lambda = 2$ to 1 cm. even for light to moderate rain the ratio may attain 0.1 while fairly heavy rain is likely to obscure the echo from aircraft.

We also see that for $r \Delta = 50$ that is for say,

$$\Delta = 10^\circ \text{ and } r = 5 \text{ Km} \cong 3.1 \text{ miles}$$

the value of $r^2 \Delta^2$ is 10 times that for $r \Delta = 16$ so that the upper horizontal line in Figure (3) will apply for $k = 1.0$ instead of $k = 0.1$ when, for example, $G = 3$. It will be appreciated that, for given $r \Delta$ a horizontal line drawn n units below the existing one will correspond to a value of k of 10^{-n} times that associated with the original.

For ready reference, some typical values are given on the right hand side of both the horizontal lines in Figure (3).

The obliteration and masking effects, produced by heavy storms with the shorter wavelengths, will be discussed fully below in Section (14) where the effect of attenuation is considered.

(10) COMPARISON WITH OBSERVATION.

The essential parts of the above calculations were completed in a rough form nearly a year ago, and it was confidently expected that echoes from heavy rain would be observed, although none had then been reported. The first case occurred early this year on February 20th. A heavy cumulo-nimbus cloud from which fell a shower of hail, was observed at T.R.E. to produce marked echoes with a wavelength of about 10 cm. and the cloud was followed out to sea to a distance of 7 miles. The

hailstones in this case were only about 0.3 cm. in diameter.

This observation was interesting and indicated that the effects of the kind predicted actually occurred. At that time the theory had not been worked out for ice so that a quantitative check was not then possible. The computations for ice have now been completed and this case will be treated below in another section and the predictions compared with observation.

Subsequently, after the likelihood of cloud echoes had been discussed with Professor Oliphant, he reported an observation of a storm on April 19th, and this enabled the first quantitative comparison to be made. The data are as follows:-

The wavelength used was 6.7 cm. and the pulse length one and a half microseconds so that $\tau = 0.5$ Km. approximately. The total beam divergence $\Delta = 2.2^\circ$ corresponding to half intensity of the principal lobe.

Heavy rain fell and the diameter D of the drops when the cloud was overhead was estimated roughly at 0.25 cm. When the cloud was at a distance of 8 Km. the height of the cloud echo trace on the C.R.T. was estimated to be of the order of one tenth that of an aircraft; the angle of elevation of the beam was then 25° . From the angle of elevation and the distance r of 8 Km., it would follow that the observed echo was produced from that portion of the cloud lying between 3 and 4 Km. above the ground. Now cumulo-nimbus clouds over England extend, on the average, to about 4 to 5 Km. above ground level and the cloud base is generally at a height of about 1 Km. It would thus appear that, when the observation was made, the beam was passing through the upper half of the cloud and it is to be expected that the droplet diameter would be smaller there than on arrival at the ground.

The precipitation was described as 'Heavy Rain' which corresponds to our reference number (4) but the drop diameter was very roughly estimated to be 0.25 cm. and this would correspond to more than the meteorological designation "Excessive Rain", reference No.(3). A fair estimate for the conditions obtaining in the upper half of the cloud would seem to be about (4), and this value we shall adopt.

Next we must consider the value of k corresponding to the observation that the height of the echo trace on the C.R.T. for $r = 8$ Km., was of the order of one tenth that of an aircraft, at the same distance, if the cloud had been absent. Now k refers to the ratio of the intensities of the echoes from a cloud and the aircraft within it, but the ratio of the heights of the echo traces on a C.R.T. will be proportional to the square root of k since the deflection of the electron beam is proportional to voltage while radiation intensity has the dimensions of voltage squared. We assume, of course, that there is no distortion in the receiver and that saturation is not attained. It follows that, since the observed ratio of peaks in the C.R.T. was about one tenth, the corresponding value of k is about 0.01. It will be shown below that the effects of attenuation for the conditions obtaining in these observations can be neglected so that the fact that the comparison was with an aircraft not in the cloud is, in this case, immaterial.

We can now proceed at once to the comparison of the observed value of k with that predicted by the theory. For $r = 8$ Km. and $\Delta = 2:2$ we have $r \Delta = 17.5$ which, on the scale of Figure (3), is indistinguishable from $r \Delta = 16$ for which the horizontal lines have already been drawn for $k = 0.01$ and $k = 0.1$.

A glance at Figure (3) then shows that the vertical from $\lambda = 6.7$ cm. intersects the curve, reference No.(4), close to the horizontal line for $k = 0.01$ (shown dashed) for $G = 3$; for $G = 1$, k would be 0.1.

Close agreement with the observations is thus obtained if we take $G = 3$. Thus the ratio of intensities is predicted to within a factor of 10 or the ratio of the heights of the echo traces to within a factor of about 3. The agreement is quite as good as we have any right to expect.

The fact that we need to take $G = 3$ rather than $G = 1$ to obtain close agreement may be interpreted as indicating that the actual aircraft back scattered somewhat more powerfully than the solid sphere taken as standard. It may be mentioned that the sphere dimension was chosen at the commencement of this work, some time before any observations of the back scatter from rain had been made.

A more accurate estimate of the value of G for various aircraft presenting different aspects to the transmitter must await further observations.

It may be noted that for aircraft of similar form, presenting the same aspect, it is to be expected that the corresponding values of G will be proportional to the square root of the projected areas.

Since this part of the report was written, a further observation was made at T.R.E. using 3 cm. waves. A value of k of as high as 5 to 10 was observed at a distance of 8 to 9 miles ≈ 13.5 Km. from a dark cloud (nimbus). Since Δ was about 4:5, the product $r \Delta = 60$. From the description of the cloud it seems probable that the droplets within it correspond roughly to a condition between our reference numbers (4) and (5). From Figure (3) we then see that we should expect a value of k about 1.5 for $G = 3$, or 15 for $G = 1$. This is again in conformity with the observations.

(11) THE REFRACTIVE INDEX AND ABSORPTION COEFFICIENT OF ICE.

We have seen in Figures(1) and (4) how, in the case of water, a rapid drop of the refractive index from the static value of 8.95 to a much lower value occurs in the neighbourhood of the powerful absorption band near $\lambda = 2$ cm. This anomalous dispersion is due to the polar water molecule. Now Errera (8) has found that solids, which on melting produce polar molecules, show anomalous dispersion even when in the solid state. It appears, in fact, that a solid like ice behaves as if it were a polar liquid with very high internal friction which increases as the temperature is reduced. Thus, corresponding to the absorption band at $\lambda = 2$ cm. for water, it is found that, for example, with ice at -2°C . a band appears at $\lambda = 45$ Km. while at -12°C . it moves out as far as $\lambda = 190$ Km.

At/

(8) J. Errera. J. de Physique 5, p.304, 1924.

At the longer wavelengths, values of n and $n\chi$ for ice can be derived, by the use of (21) to (24), from the work of Errera mentioned above, together with observations by Gutton (9) and Granier (10). Also, Cartwright (11) gives some values of $n\chi$ in the far infra red region.

The values obtained are plotted in Figure (4) which also shows the corresponding curves for water, down to the near infra red. The $n\chi$ curve for ice at -2°C . is derived from measurements by Errera and this has been extended to wavelengths below 8 Km. by displacing the very similar curve for -12°C . deduced from Granier's data. The n curve has been extended down to about $\lambda = 100$ cm. by the use of Gutton's results.

It is unfortunate that no data are available over the wavelength range in which we are primarily interested, namely from 100 to 1 cm. It seems probable, however, that in this region n will not be far from 1.6, corresponding to the extrapolation shown by the dashed line. As regards $n\chi$, it would appear from Granier's results that the curve will fall to quite low values at about $\lambda = 300$ cm. At still shorter wavelengths, the curve would be expected to rise again, as near 0.01 cm., other peaks may occur, but it does not seem possible to predict $n\chi$ values over the range $\lambda = 100$ to 1 cm. Nevertheless, an estimate of an upper limit may be made. It will be noted that the value of χ for ice at the peak near $\lambda = 45$ Km. is closely the same as that at the corresponding peak near $\lambda = 2$ cm. in the case of water; both are about 0.34. It is reasonable to assume that χ for ice over our wavelength range will lie between zero and 0.5, which is an estimate of χ for the far infra red band of water; the actual value is probably quite small. We shall see in the next section that the above assumption is sufficient for us to proceed with an investigation of the echo intensity from ice particles. On the other hand, we shall be unable to compute values of the attenuation since this depends so greatly upon the values of χ .

(12) THE ECHO INTENSITY FROM CIRRUS TYPE CLOUDS AND HAILSTORMS.

Adopting a constant value of $n = 1.6$ for ice within our wavelength range, values of the function (25) were computed for a series of values of χ . The results show that for values of χ up to 0.5 the approximate expression (28b) is valid for D/λ as high as 0.15; this figure is appreciably higher than the limiting value of D/λ for water which we found to be 0.03. The increase is due to the lower value of n for ice.

Next, for $n = 1.6$, the value of the function of n and $n\chi$ on the right hand side of (28b) is found to be 0.117 if $\chi = 0$ and 0.33 if $\chi = 0.5$. For our purpose the change is small. It is true that for $\chi = 0.5$ the value of (28b) is some three times greater than for $\chi = 0$, but on a diagram for ice similar to Figure (3), this makes little difference, particularly if the diagram is constructed for the intermediate value 0.25 corresponding to $\chi = 0.37$.

The/

(9) Gutton, Comptes Rendues 130.p.1119, 1900.

(10) Granier, Comptes Rendues 179. p.1314, 1924.

See also Debye, Polar Molecules, p.107, 1929, and Int.Crit.Tables, Vol.6. p.78.

(11) C.H.Cartwright, Nature 136, p.181. 1935.

The diagram will then, in fact, be amply accurate for our purposes, whatever the true values of χ may be, provided they do not materially exceed 0.5. Also, changes in the constants, due to temperature, will not produce any appreciable modifications, unless n varies more than would appear from the published data.

Taking the intermediate value 0.25 for the above mentioned function in (28b), we find from (28b) and (33),

$$\frac{k G^2}{r^2 \Delta^2} = 5.05 \cdot 10^7 \frac{N D^6}{\lambda^4} \quad (34)$$

We can now proceed to estimate the echo intensity, first, from cirrus and similar high lying clouds, and second, from hailstorms.

Cirrus and other high clouds formed at temperatures well below 0°C. usually consist of small snow crystals or ice spicules. Occasionally, however, these clouds may be composed of supercooled water droplets.

The average height of true cirrus cloud is 9-12 Km. and about 8 Km. in the case of cirro-stratus, which is considerably denser than the former. The height of cirro-cumulus, which produces the well known "Mackerel Sky" is lower still and is generally some 5 to 7 Km. Below this level, clouds composed of ice particles are rare.

The particle diameters in these clouds lie between 0.005 and 0.0002 cm., while the concentration tends to be less, and generally much less, than that of lower lying clouds. We shall, therefore, adopt, as a rough upper limit, the values, $D = 0.003$ cm. and $N = 10$. This value of N is about one tenth that of a typical fine weather strato-cumulus cloud.

We now obtain from (34),

$$\log_{10} \frac{k G^2}{r^2 \Delta^2} = 7.70 + \log_{10} \frac{N D^6}{\lambda^4} \quad (35)$$

from which a plot shown in Figure (5) can be constructed on the same lines as Figure (3). The line, marked $D = 0.003$, $N = 10$, which represents the upper limit for high lying clouds composed of ice particles is shown near the bottom of Figure (5) together with two other cases, namely for $D = 0.001$, $N = 10^3$ and $N = 10$. The horizontal lines at the top of the graph have the same significance as in Figure (3). The curved dotted line, seen at the top, shows roughly the limit of the validity of (35).

From Figure (5) it is immediately clear that even down to a wavelength of 1 cm., the back scattered radiation from all high lying cirrus type clouds will be quite inappreciable. The back scattered intensity

will/

will, indeed, be so small that further investigation of the effect of the deviation of the crystals from a spherical form need not be pursued.

Similarly, we can dismiss the case of high lying clouds composed of supercooled water droplets.

We now come to the more interesting case of hailstorms. Curves derived from (35) are shown in Figure (5) for a series of hailstone diameters up to 2 cm.

As regards the values of N adopted, these, for diameters up to 0.3, correspond with the values given in Table (2), and are probably sufficiently accurate for our purpose. For the larger diameters, use was made of the empirical rule that the effect of the many factors determining the relation between typical values of N and D results in a more or less constant product ND^2 . That this is so can be seen from a consideration of the upper portion of Table (2). We have taken $ND^2 = 3.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and we assume that the rule applies, at least roughly, for hail.

The full and the dashed horizontal lines at the top of the figure correspond with those of Figure (3) and typical values of k for various values of Δ are given on the right for $G = 3$.

We can now immediately compare the theory with the T.R.E. observations of February 20th mentioned in Section (10). The diameter of the hailstones was 0.3 cm. and these produced marked echoes with a wavelength of about 10 cm. although none was observable with 3 metres. From Figure (5) we see that at 10 cm. an average fall of hailstones 0.3 cm. in diameter would be expected to lead to a value of $k = 0.03$ for $\Delta = 16$, or $k = 0.3$ for $\Delta = 50$. Hence, the ratio of the heights of the echo traces from the storm and from an aircraft within it would be expected to lie between 0.17 and 0.55.

On the other hand, for a wavelength of 3 metres, the values of k would be 10^{-6} of the above, and thus the echo height, due to the storm, would be quite inappreciable.

Although a detailed quantitative comparison is not possible in this case it will, however, be seen that the theory is again in general accord with the observations.

Summarising, we see that the smallest hailstone diameters which for various wavelengths will produce marked echoes are roughly as given in Table (3).

Table (3).

Least Hailstone diameter to produce marked echoes.

λ cm.	D cm.	N
50	1.7	1.2 10^{-5}
25	0.7	7.2 10^{-5}
10	0.3	3.8 10^{-4}
5	0.2	3.8 10^{-4}
3	0.1	5.3 10^{-4}

(13) EFFECTS FROM TROPICAL SAND AND DUST-STORMS.

It may be of interest to discuss briefly the echo intensity from sand and dust-storms, as these might affect operations in the tropics.

Desert sand is generally composed of rounded crystalline quartz grains whose sizes according to R.A.Bagnold (12) may range from 0.001 cm. up to 0.3 cm. in diameter. Bagnold's determination of size-distributions of desert sands in Libya shows that the peaks correspond to never less than about 0.01 cm. and are usually between 0.015 and 0.03 cm. When such sand is being driven by wind the grains rarely rise to a height of more than a metre on sand dunes, or 2 metres over rough ground. Unless finer particles, defined as dust, are present, the air above this height is relatively clear and, in a true sand-storm, people's heads may often appear above the dense cloud of driven sand "as from the water of a swimming bath".

It can be deduced from data given by Bagnold that the average concentration of sand up to a height of one metre may be up to 100 grams per cubic metre, while the average concentration up to one cm. above the surface may reach a value as high as 7500 grams per cubic metre. These are for a wind velocity of 16 m. per sec. measured at 1 metre above the ground. More usual concentrations would be expected to be one half or one third of the above values.

When, on the other hand, the wind is blowing over alluvial ground, with little or no sand, as in Iraq, the dust rises in dense clouds, sometimes to a height of several thousand feet, and the sun is obscured for a long period. This corresponds to a dust-storm as distinct from the true sand-storm, which keeps mainly quite close to the ground.

No data on the concentration of particles in dust-storms appear to be available, but rough estimates of the mass per unit volume of air can be arrived at as follows:-

Suppose that a layer of dust 1 cm. in thickness is removed from the surface by a violent wind and carried up as a cloud to a height of 1000 feet or say 0.3 Km. The mass raised per sq.m. of surface is $2 \cdot 10^4$ grams so that the concentration would be about 70 grams per cubic metre. It would thus appear likely that a concentration of a few hundred grams per cubic metre would not often be exceeded, except perhaps locally.

The refractive index of quartz for long waves is 2.1 and for visible light is 1.55. No determinations seem available for the range of wavelengths which interest us but it seems probable that, down to 1 cm., it will not be far from the long wave value. Furthermore, it is known that down to 3 cm. at least, the absorption index is very low compared with water. On the other hand, the presence of the small quantity of iron, which is present in sands and dust, is likely to raise the value of χ somewhat, but it is doubtful if this value would be sufficiently high for the approximate expression (28) to be much in error. From (28) and (33) we

then/

(12) R.A.Bagnold. The Physics of Blown Sand and Desert Dunes, 1941. I am indebted to Professor Rankine for having drawn my attention to Bagnold's work.

then obtain, with $n^2 = 4.5$,

$$\log_{10} \frac{k G^2}{n^2 \Delta^2} = 8.2 + \log_{10} \frac{N D^6}{\lambda^4} \quad (36)$$

From our discussion of Figure (3), it follows that the echo intensity may become sensible, in comparison with that from an aircraft, if the right hand side of (36) is about 4.6; this corresponds to the horizontal dashed line marked on Figures (3) and (5). We thus see that the echo may become appreciable when

$$\frac{N D^6}{\lambda^4} \geq 2.5 \cdot 10^{-12} \quad (37)$$

If now we let M be the mass of sand or dust per cubic metre of air we have

$$M = \frac{\pi}{6} 10^6 \rho N D^3 \quad (38)$$

where ρ is the density of the particles. Eliminating N and taking $\rho = 2.7$, we find that the minimum mass M' of sand or dust, per cubic metre of air, that is necessary to produce an appreciable echo, compared with that from an aircraft, will be given by,

$$M' = 3.5 \cdot 10^{-6} \frac{\lambda^4}{D^3} \quad (39)$$

It may be noted that, from (28) or (28b), it follows that the echo from a given mass M of material will decrease rapidly as the given mass is subdivided into smaller and smaller particles; in fact, the intensity is proportional to $\frac{D^3 M}{\lambda^4}$ even up to grain sizes larger than we are concerned with here.

By means of (39) we can now construct the following Table.

Table 4.

Minimum Mass of Sand or Dust, per cubic metre of Air, necessary to produce an appreciable echo compared with that from an Aircraft. It is assumed that $\chi = 0$.

	Grain Diameter D in cm.	Approx. Rate of fall m/sec.	Values of M' g/cu.m.		
			$\lambda = 10$ cm.	$\lambda = 3$ cm.	$\lambda = 1$ cm.
True Sand-Storms (Particles seldom rise more than 2 m. above surface).	0.1	6.3	35	0.29	0.004
	0.05	3.0	280	2.3	0.03
	0.02	1.0	4400	36	0.44
	0.01	0.4		290	3.5
True Dust-storms (Particles may be carried up in dense clouds to several thousand feet).	0.005	0.15		2300	28
	0.002	0.04			440
	0.001	0.01			3530
	0.0005	0.0025			
	0.0002	0.0005			

Now we have estimated that, in the case of dust-storms, M is seldom likely to exceed a few hundred grams per cubic metre*, and that this limit also applies to sand-storms, except very near the ground. It follows from Table (4) that, for a wavelength of 10 cm., no echoes are likely to be observed. This is because the only value of M' below our limit is for the largest sand particles and these have such a high rate of fall that they are never likely to form the necessary dense cloud at a height of more than a few cm. above the surface of the ground. For a wavelength of 3 cm. the effect is more marked in the case of sand-storms, and it is possible that the echo from the sand might obscure echoes from objects on the ground; but no appreciable echoes are likely to occur from dust-storms. On the other hand, if the wavelength is reduced to 1 cm., echoes may be expected to appear in the case of dense dust-storms, provided the particles are not too fine.

To conclude this section, one other phenomenon may be considered. During the heat of the day, over any hot dusty region, small local whirlwinds may develop due to violent convection; these are known as 'dust-devils'. Their diameter is generally only a matter of yards, but surface dust is picked up and raised in a very dense column, to 1000 or 2000 feet. No evidence is available to indicate whether larger particles are picked up by these whirlwinds than are lifted by the high winds producing dust-storms. Should this be the case, then echoes at wavelengths below about 7 cm., may be produced, otherwise, appreciable echoes would not be expected until the wavelength is reduced to about 1 cm.

(14)/

* According to W.E.Gibbs, Clouds and Smokes (1936), Grain Elevator air may contain as much as 1000 g./cu.m. of particles whose average diameter is 0.0015 cm.

(14) EFFECT OF ATTENUATION ON THE ECHO INTENSITY.
OBLITERATION AND MASKING EFFECTS.

Up to the present we have assumed that the attenuation due to absorption and scattering by the droplets is negligible. This, as we shall see, is the case for the longer wavelengths but it is by no means true for the large droplets at short wavelengths.

The attenuation constant will be defined by the equation,

$$I = I_0 e^{-\sigma r} \quad (40)$$

where, as usual, r is measured in Km, so that σ is in Km^{-1} .

To allow for the attenuation, it follows that equations (3), (6) and (11) must be multiplied by a factor K given by,

$$K = \left(\frac{r^2}{h} - \frac{h}{4} \right) \int_{r_1}^{r_2} \frac{e^{-\sigma(r-R)}}{r^2} dr. \quad (41)$$

in which,

$$r_1 = r - \frac{h}{2} \quad r_2 = r + \frac{h}{2} \quad (42)$$

also

$$\frac{1}{\frac{1}{r_1} - \frac{1}{r_2}} = \frac{r^2}{h} - \frac{h}{4} \quad (43)$$

and where R in (41), is the distance from the transmitter to the nearer boundary of the cloud or rain, and r , as usual, is the distance to the centre of the pulse. We shall assume that $R < r_1$. It may be shown, see Appendix 2(F), that for $r > 2.5$ Km. and for a value of h about half a kilometre, we may write (41), with an error not exceeding about 20%.

$$K \doteq e^{-2\sigma d} \frac{\sinh \sigma h}{\sigma h} \quad (44)$$

where $d = r - R$

is/

is the distance of the centre of the pulse from the near boundary of the cloud.

Suppose that the cloud of droplets has a sharp boundary past which the droplet size and concentration is uniform. Then, as the pulse enters the cloud, the intensity of the echo sent back to the transmitter will increase to a maximum after which, if there is no attenuation, the intensity will fall off as $1/r^2$. If, however, there is appreciable attenuation in the cloud the maximum intensity will be less and the fall off more rapid. Now it is easily seen that, in the simple case of a rectangular pulse, the echo peak will occur when the pulse has just fully entered the cloud, that is when

$$r - \frac{L}{2} = R \quad (45)$$

Thus for $L = 0.5$ we have,

$$d = r - R = \frac{1}{4}$$

Substituting in (44) we find the ratio K_m of the echo peak intensity, to that if there were no attenuation, will be given by

$$K_m = e^{-\frac{\sigma}{2}} \frac{\sinh \sigma/2}{\sigma/2} \quad (46)$$

The whole question of attenuation from the aspect of point to point transmission will be fully discussed in the next section in which values of σ will be computed. Utilising these results for our present purpose, values of the factor (46) have been calculated and are given in Table (5) for various wavelengths and conditions.

Table (5).

Values of the Factor (46) by which the Echo Peak Intensity is reduced by Attenuation. Centre of Pulse 0.25 Km. inside Cloud Boundary.

	Light Rain.	Mod. Rain.	Heavy Rain & Thunderstorms.			
Ref.No. (Table 2).	(6)	(5)	(4)	(3)	(2)	(1)
$\lambda = 1$ cm.	0.99	0.97	0.84	0.51	0.097	(0.01)
2	0.998	0.99	0.96	0.85	0.45	0.10
3	1.00	1.00	0.99	0.96	0.78	0.39
5	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.99	0.96	0.84
10	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.99	0.98
20	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.998

This shows that in all the cases in which we compared the theory with observation, the neglect of attenuation was/

was justified. On the other hand, for short wavelengths and the heavier storms the effect becomes appreciable. In fact, for these cases, when we consider the form of the whole echo instead of just its peak value, the effect of attenuation is more marked than would appear from the above Table. As an illustration, let us assume that the cloud is a layer, some 5 Km. in thickness, with sharp boundaries between which the droplet size and concentration is uniform. Also, for simplicity, let us assume that the pulse is rectangular and that the transmitter is so far away from the cloud that the diminution of intensity, due to the inverse square law, is negligible. Then, if there is no attenuation, the echo intensity will rapidly rise as the pulse passes over the near boundary and will then remain constant until the corresponding rapid drop which occurs as the pulse passes over the far boundary. On the other hand, when the attenuation constant is appreciable the echo intensity will rise, but less rapidly than before, and then pass through a maximum and rapidly diminish. A number of cases, computed from (44), are tabulated in Appendix (3) and plotted in Figure (6) for wavelengths of 10, 3 and 1 cm. All are relative to the case of zero attenuation.

For $\lambda = 10$ cm. we see from Figure (6) that, only in the case of very severe thunderstorms, will any attenuation be apparent, but at $\lambda = 3$ and $\lambda = 1$ cm. marked effects may occur. The most important of these is that very heavy rain and thunderstorms may not only obliterate the echoes from aircraft within them, but may actually mask objects behind them. We have already seen, from Figure (3), that, for wavelengths of 3 cm. and below, obliteration of aircraft echoes may occur with very heavy rain and severe thunderstorms due to the greater echo intensity from the cloud. But, if there were no attenuation, masking of aircraft behind the cloud would not occur, and the effect would not be serious, since aircraft would not generally fly inside severe storm clouds. We now see, however, that owing to attenuation, the much more serious masking effect can occur. Thus for $\lambda = 3$ cm. a cloud corresponding to reference No.(2) would, if more than say 4 Km. in thickness, mask completely any aircraft behind it, while for reference No.(1) a cloud half a kilometer in thickness would suffice; these conditions are, however, probably rare, at least in this country. At a wavelength of 1 cm., however, the masking effect will be seen to be much greater. Thus 'heavy Rain', reference No.(4), if 5 Km. in depth, would produce serious masking while a 1.5 Km. layer of 'Very Heavy Rain', reference No.(3) will do the same.

Again, for a wavelength of 1 cm. and severe thunderstorms or conditions corresponding to reference Numbers (2) and (1) another remarkable effect may occur. We see that, on the scale of the diagram, the curve for reference number (1) has vanished, and even (2) has nearly disappeared. Thus, under these conditions, the beam might be pointed in the direction of the storm, behind which there were aircraft, and then, not only would no echoes be observed from the aircraft, but there would be no indication that the cloud was there!

As regards the ratio k of the echo intensities from the cloud and an object within it, this will, to a first approximation, remain as given by equations (9) and (10) since both will be attenuated in much the

same/

same way.* The only point to be borne in mind is that, as mentioned in the last paragraph, both echoes may be reduced or may even vanish when the attenuation is large.

If appreciable, the factor K must, however, be allowed for when a comparison is being made between the echo from a cloud and the echo from an aircraft at the same distance when the cloud is absent. This case arose above, when comparing the theory with Professor Oliphant's observations. But since, for $\lambda = 7$, the values in Table (5) are practically unity, even for the case, reference No.(2) we see that no allowance for attenuation is necessary. At shorter wavelengths, however, due allowance must be made in any similar comparison.

(15) THE RELATIVE ECHO INTENSITY FOR DIFFERENT WAVELENGTHS.

Before proceeding, it may be of interest to tabulate the relative echo peak intensities, for wavelengths of 10, 3 and 1 cm. allowing for the attenuation. The attenuation factor was computed by (46) and thus the values given refer to echo peak intensities. In practice, finite resolution of the receiver may reduce the heights of the sharper peaks. See Figure (6). For the smaller droplet sizes we see by (28b) that, were it not for attenuation, the relative echo intensities for 10 and 3 cm. would be as 1:123 and for 3 and 1 cm. as 1:81. For a single sphere large compared with the wavelength and composed of a material such that n and χ are constant from $\lambda = 1$ to 10 cm., the ratios will, of course, be unity in each case.

Table (6).

Relative Peak Echo Intensities. Pulse Length $K = 0.5$ Km.

Conditions Corresponding to Ref. Nos. in Table (2).	Ratio of echo peak intensity for $\lambda = 3$ cm. to that for $\lambda = 10$ cm.	Corresponding ratio for $\lambda = 1$ cm. to that for $\lambda = 3$ cm.
Thunderstorms and Very Heavy Rain. (1)	25	0.41
(2)	62	2.0
(3)	100	11.7
Heavy Rain (4)	120	34
Moderate Rain (5)	123	61
Light Rain (6)	123	79
Clouds with small droplets.	123	81
Single spheres, large compared with the wavelength. Constant n and χ .	1.0	1.0

* Except for the cases $\lambda = 1$ cm. reference numbers (1) and (2) and $\lambda = 3$ cm. reference number (1). In these cases, the sinh factor in (44) makes a very material difference. The reason is that, when σ is large, then owing to the width of the pulse, the reduction of the aircraft echo by the attenuation effect will be greater than that of the cloud echo intensity, when the pulse is at the same distance.

It will be seen that, owing to the deviation from the inverse fourth power law in the case of the larger droplets and also owing to the attenuation, the ratios towards the top of the Table rapidly diminish. It is interesting to see that for very severe thunderstorms, more strictly for conditions corresponding to our reference number (1), the echo intensity may actually be less at a wavelength of 1 cm. than it is at 3 cm.

(16) THE ATTENUATION IN THE CASE OF POINT TO POINT TRANSMISSION.

Although no previous detailed computations of the echo intensity from rain etc. have been published, the problem of the attenuation has been considered by Stratton (13) and by Fränz (14).

Stratton assumed that the absorption index χ would be entirely negligible down to $\lambda = 5$ cms. and he based his actual computations on a simple expression similar to (51) taking $\chi = 0$. He thus obtained only the loss of radiation from the primary beam due to scattering alone. In consequence, Stratton's values of σ are many orders of magnitude lower than the values calculated here on the basis of the values of $n\chi$ adopted from the published data and given in Table (1). Also, it should be pointed out that Stratton has worked out his expansions only for real and not for complex m .

Fränz considers the case when the absorption cannot be neglected but he assumed that the particle diameter is so small that only the first term in our (49) below is appreciable. He is, in fact, concerned only with mists, fogs and fine weather clouds containing droplets smaller than normal rain. The values he obtains for $M = 1$ are shown by the circles on Figure 7. It will be seen that they fall closely on our curve for small drops. His conclusion that the attenuation depends only on the total quantity of liquid water and not on the drop size is valid only for small droplets, and, as we shall see, Figure (8) it leads to a considerable underestimate of the attenuation in the case of large drops at the shorter wavelengths.

We will now develop expressions valid for the computation of the attenuation in the case of the largest drops we need to consider and for any value of the absorption index. It must be emphasised that the attenuation depends greatly on $n\chi$, so that the accuracy of the values of the attenuation constant derived is dependent on the accuracy of the observations of the absorption index for liquid water given in the literature.

When the outgoing beam passes over particles in its path, its intensity is attenuated due to two causes, namely by the true absorption of energy by the particles and by the loss of energy from the beam due to scattering. The latter is not, of course, just the scattering in the backward direction alone, given by (12), but is the total loss due to scattering in all directions.

Either/

(13) Stratton. Proc. Inst. Radio Eng. 18. p.1064. 1930.

(14) K. Fränz. Hochfrequenztechnik und Electroakustik. 55. p.141. 1940.

(I am indebted to Sir Edward Appleton, for this reference).

Either the true absorption or the loss by scattering can be computed separately once the amplitudes a_ν and p_ν of the partial waves have been determined. We are, however, interested in the sum of the two losses mentioned and this, for one droplet can be shown to be

$$A = \frac{\lambda^2}{2\pi} A_i \quad (45)$$

where A_i is the imaginary part of

$$\sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} (-1)^\nu (a_\nu - p_\nu) \quad (46)$$

Then the attenuation of a parallel beam, traversing a thickness x of a suspension of the particles, having N particles per unit volume, will be given by

$$I = I_0 e^{-\sigma x} \quad (47)$$

in which

$$\sigma = NA \quad (48)$$

Then, from the expressions for the partial waves, a_1, a_2 and p_1 given in Appendix (1), we find, for σ in cm^{-1} ,

$$\sigma = \frac{\lambda^2}{2\pi} N \alpha^3 \left\{ c_1 + c_2 \alpha^2 + c_3 \alpha^3 \right\} \quad (49)$$

in which the c 's are given by

$$\begin{aligned} c_1 &= r_1 \\ c_2 &= r_2 + v_1 + w_2 \\ c_3 &= r_3 \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

These coefficients are the functions of q and h given in Appendix (1) together with a table of their numerical values.

Now, if the absorption index χ is zero, then the coefficients C_1 and C_2 are also zero and (49) becomes, after substituting (16) and putting $k = 0$ in the expression for σ , in Appendix (1),

$$\sigma_{(\chi=0)} = \frac{2\pi^5}{3} \frac{ND^6}{\lambda^4} \left(\frac{n^2-1}{n^2+2} \right)^2 \quad (51)$$

so that σ is proportional to the sixth power of the diameter and varies inversely as the fourth power of the wavelength.

The law is, however, quite different if χ is appreciable, for then the first two terms in (49) are no longer zero. Suppose, for example, that, for given χ the particle diameter is sufficiently small for the second and third terms in (49) to be neglected. Then we have as a second special case,

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma &= \frac{3\pi}{\lambda} M \cdot 10^{-6} C_1 \\ &= \frac{18\pi}{\lambda} M \cdot 10^{-6} \frac{k}{(q+2)^2 + k^2} \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

in which

$$M = 10^6 \frac{\pi}{G} ND^3 \quad (53)$$

Here M is the mass of liquid water in grams per cubic metre of air. Values of M are tabulated in the last column of Table (2), p.(11).

We now see that σ is inversely proportional to the wavelength and is directly proportional to the quantity of liquid water per unit volume, irrespective of the particle diameter.

If, however, the particle diameter is not so small that the second and third terms of (49) can be neglected in comparison with the first, then, for the same mass M of liquid water, the value of σ will be greater for large particles than for small ones. This applies to many of the cases with which we shall deal.

Firstly, let us consider the case of fogs, mists and stratus cloud, the latter corresponding to an ordinary overcast sky. For all these cases (52) will apply and a family of curves connecting $\log_{10} \frac{\sigma_{k, \chi}}{\sigma_{k, 0}}$ with wavelength is shown in Figure (7) for various values of M . On the right hand side, a scale of the db. loss per Km. has been drawn.

The curves cover cases from $M = 0.01$, corresponding to fog and light mists, up to $M = 10$ which would correspond to extremely dense cloud. A special curve, shown by the dashed line, is for a typical stratus or fine weather strato-cumulus cloud. As a further guide, it may be mentioned that $M = 0.75$, $D = 0.003$ cm., corresponds to only light cloud through which objects would be seen at a distance of 70 metres.

It will be seen that the attenuation is small for the longer wavelengths, but that for $\lambda = 3$ it may attain 0.5 db. per Km. although for a typical stratus cloud it is 0.1 to 0.2 db. per Km.

The small circles close to the curve for $M = 1$ are those computed by Fränz in the paper mentioned in the introduction to this section.

We will next consider the attenuation in rain clouds and all cases where the droplet diameter is more than about 0.05 cm. For this purpose, the full expression (49) must be used. The necessary coefficients were computed and are given in Appendix (1), Table (A).

To illustrate the fact, mentioned above, that for the same mass M of liquid water, the attenuation will be greater for large particles than for small ones, Figure (8) has been prepared. In this Figure, for each of two values of M namely 0.83 and 9.2, two curves are given, one, shown dotted, corresponds to the family shown in Figure (7) for small droplets and the other is for drops of much greater size. For the latter curves, drop diameters of 0.15 cm. and 0.5 cm. have been chosen; these correspond to our reference numbers (4) and (1) in Table (2) and are for typical heavy rain and very heavy thunderstorm conditions respectively.

Curves for a number of cases defined in Table (2) are given in Figure (9); these together with those in Figure (7) complete the series of meteorological conditions corresponding to the reference numbers (1) to (11).

It will be seen that, for a wavelength of 3 cm., the attenuation can reach 10 db. per Km. in the worst thunderstorm conditions, while for wavelengths of about 1 cm. the attenuation may reach 200 db. per Km.

In default of observational data on χ for ice and desert sand, it is unfortunately impossible to compute similar curves for hail, dust and sandstorms over the wavelength range in which we are interested. One point should, however, be mentioned. We have seen in Figure (4) that, corresponding to the strong absorption band at $\lambda = 2$ cm. in water, there is a powerful band in ice, which occurs at $\lambda = 45$ Km. for a temperature of -2°C . and which moves out to $\lambda = 190$ Km. at -12°C . It might be thought that this absorption band would produce appreciable attenuation at the corresponding long wavelengths, but a glance at (52) shows that, since λ occurs in the denominator, the values of σ will be negligible. In fact, for a hailstorm with hailstones at -2°C . and a wavelength of 45 Km. we find that σ will be only of the order of 10^{-6} times that of water drops when $\lambda = 2$ cm.

(17) SYNOPSIS OF PART II.

In Part II of this Report, the refractive indices of clouds containing large droplets will be determined. These can be calculated from the coefficients which we have already computed. The echo intensity from spheres of a size comparable with and much larger than the wavelength will also be treated and the derivation of (30) will be given. A point of interest is that, for a given total large mass of particles, there is a size of particle for which the echo intensity from the whole will be a maximum. This optimum size will be determined for different materials; in general, it is roughly of the order of the wavelength. The obliteration and masking effects discussed at the end of Section (14) will be considered in more detail.

The attenuation and masking effects due to hail; also the echo intensity from and the attenuation caused by sea spray, salt water drops and snowstorms will have to await accurate measurements of n and γ for sea water and ice.

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CHECKED BY: J.W.R. & B.S.C.

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APPROVED BY: J.W.R.

APPENDIX (1).Expressions for a_n and p_n when m is complex.

Following the procedure outlined in Section (3) we obtain for the first few partial wave coefficients:-

$$a_1 = \alpha^3 \left[(q_1 + q_2 \alpha^2 + q_3 \alpha^3) - i (r_1 + r_2 \alpha^2 + r_3 \alpha^3) \right]$$

$$a_2 = \alpha^5 \left[-u_1 + i v_1 \right]$$

$$p_1 = \alpha^5 \left[-w_1 + i w_2 \right]$$

in which, if $m^2 = g + i h$

$$q_1 = 2 \frac{(g-1)(g+2) + h^2}{(g+2)^2 + h^2}$$

$$q_2 = \frac{6}{5} \frac{(g-1)(g-2)(g+2)^2 + h^2 \{2(g+1)^2 - (g+20)\} + h^4}{\{(g+2)^2 + h^2\}^2}$$

$$q_3 = 8 \frac{h \{(g-1)(g+2) + h^2\}}{\{(g+2)^2 + h^2\}^2}$$

$$r_1 = 6 \frac{h}{(g+2)^2 + h^2}$$

$$r_2 = \frac{6}{5} \frac{h \{3(g+2)^2 - 2(g+16) + 7h^2\}}{\{(g+2)^2 + h^2\}^2}$$

$$r_3 = \frac{4}{3} \frac{(g-1)^2(g+2)^2 + h^2 \{2(g-1)(g+2) - 9\} + h^4}{\{(g+2)^2 + h^2\}^2}$$

$$u_1 = \frac{1}{3} \frac{(g-1)(2g+3) + 2h^2}{(2g+3)^2 + 4h^2}$$

$$v_1 = \frac{5}{3} \frac{h}{(2g+3)^2 + 4h^2}$$

$$w_1 = \frac{1}{15} (g-1)$$

$$w_2 = \frac{1}{15} h$$

The values of each of the above coefficients were worked out for $\lambda = 1, 2, 3, 5, 10$ and 20 cm. A selection of the results is given below.

Table (A).

Coefficient.	$\lambda = 1$ cm.	$\lambda = 3$ cm.	$\lambda = 10$ cm.
q_1	1.829	1.925	1.928
q_2	1.04	1.12	1.10
q_3	0.0865	0.0525	0.0124
$r_1 = c_1$	0.0696	0.0409	0.0096
r_2	0.0515	0.0314	0.0058
$r_3 = c_3$	1.14	1.238	1.236
u_1	0.157	0.1621	0.1618
v_1	0.00495	0.00286	0.000675
w_1	2.04	3.82	5.11
w_2	1.081	2.106	0.693

Next, as regards the attenuation, the values of the coefficients C_1 , C_2 and C_3 in (49) are found to be as follows:-

Table (B)/

Table (B).

Values of the coefficients in (49) for the values of g and h in Table (1).

λ cm.	C_1	C_2	C_3
1	0.0396	1.138	1.140
2	0.0548	2.552	1.235
3	0.0409	2.140	1.238
5	0.0223	1.506	1.240
10	0.0096	0.700	1.236
20	0.0082	0.600	1.235

APPENDIX (2).

Let us write $(h/2r)^2 = x$ and assume $x \ll 1$.
 Then performing the integration (38) we find, firstly
 for $\sigma r > 1$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 K = e^{-2\sigma(r-R)} & \left[\frac{\sinh \sigma h}{\sigma h} \left\{ (1 + 2x + 2x^2 + 2x^3 + \dots) \right. \right. \\
 & - \frac{1}{\sigma r} (1 + 5x + 9x^2 + 13x^3 + \dots) \\
 & + \frac{3}{2\sigma^2 r^2} (1 + 9x + 25x^2 + 49x^3 + \dots) \\
 & - \dots \dots \dots \left. \right\} \\
 & + \cosh \sigma h \left\{ \frac{1}{\sigma r} (1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + \dots) \right. \\
 & - \frac{3}{2\sigma^2 r^2} \left(1 + \frac{7}{3}x + \frac{11}{3}x^2 + \frac{15}{3}x^3 + \dots \right) \\
 & + \frac{3}{\sigma^3 r^3} (1 + 4x + 9x^2 + 16x^3 + \dots) \\
 & - \dots \dots \dots \left. \right\} \quad (A)
 \end{aligned}$$

while, secondly, for $\sigma r < 1$ we find,

$$\begin{aligned}
 K = e^{-2\sigma(r-R)} & \left[1 + 2\sigma r \left(\frac{2}{3}x + \frac{2}{15}x^2 + \frac{2}{35}x^3 + \dots \right) \right. \\
 & + (2\sigma r)^2 \left(\frac{x}{6} + \frac{2}{15}x^2 + \frac{2}{35}x^3 + \dots \right) \\
 & + (2\sigma r)^3 \left(\frac{1}{15}x^2 + \frac{1}{35}x^3 + \dots \right) \\
 & + (2\sigma r)^4 \left(\frac{1}{120}x^2 + \frac{1}{105}x^3 + \dots \right) \\
 & + \dots \dots \dots \left. \right] \quad (B)
 \end{aligned}$$

Let/

Let us assume that $r > 2.5$ Km. for the usual
 $h = 0.5$ Km; then $x < 0.01$.

We then see from (B) that for $\sigma r x < 0.1$, that is for $\sigma < 4$ we can write with an error of less than 15%,

$$K = e^{-2\sigma(r-R)} \quad (\sigma < 4) \quad (C)$$

Again for (A) we see that, with the same accuracy, and for $\sigma r > 10$, that is for $\sigma > 4$ we have,

$$K = e^{-2\sigma(r-R)} \frac{\text{and } \sigma h}{\sigma h} \left[\left(1 - \frac{1}{\sigma r}\right) + \frac{a}{\sigma h} \right] \quad (D)$$

where,

$$a = \sigma h \coth \sigma h$$

But for $\sigma h > 2$ that is for $\sigma > 4$ or $\sigma r > 10$ we have

$$a \doteq \sigma h.$$

Hence,

$$K = e^{-2\sigma(r-R)} \frac{\text{and } \sigma h}{\sigma h} \left[\left(1 - \frac{1}{\sigma r}\right) + \frac{h}{r} \right] \quad (\sigma > 4) \quad (E)$$

Now for any $r > 2.5$ and any $\sigma > 4$ the value of the square bracket lies between 0.9 and 1.2 so that, remembering our result (C), we see that we may write with an error not exceeding about 20%,

$$K = e^{-2\sigma(r-R)} \frac{\text{and } \sigma h}{\sigma h} \quad \begin{cases} R = 0.5 \\ r > 2.5 \\ 0 \leq \sigma \leq \infty \end{cases} \quad (F)$$

This is the expression (41) used in the text.

APPENDIX (3).Values of the Factor (44). Centre of Pulse
0.5 Km.inside cloud.

Reference Numbers. See Table (2).					
λ cm.	(5)	(4)	(3)	(2)	(1)
1	0.94	0.71	0.23	$5.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$(4.0 \cdot 10^{-16})$
2		0.98	0.72	0.18	$8.8 \cdot 10^{-4}$
3			0.91	0.61	0.12
5				0.91	0.70

Centre of Pulse 1.0 Km.inside cloud.

λ cm.	(5)	(4)	(3)	(2)	(1)
1	0.89	0.50	$5.1 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$2.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$(2.5 \cdot 10^{-4})$
2		0.85	0.52	$2.7 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$6.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$
3			0.84	0.38	$1.24 \cdot 10^{-2}$
5				0.84	0.49

Centre of Pulse 2.0 Km.inside cloud.

λ cm.	(5)	(4)	(3)	(2)	(1)
1	0.79	0.25	$2.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.1 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$(1.0 \cdot 10^{-97})$
2		0.72	0.27	$6.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.1 \cdot 10^{-16}$
3			0.70	0.14	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$
5				0.71	0.24

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REFRACTIVE INDEX n AND
VALUES OF $n\chi$ FOR WATER.
(SEE ALSO FIG. 4.)

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RPT. No. 7831.
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FIG. 1.

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VALUES OF
 $\text{LOG}_{10} \lambda^2 N f_0 (\alpha, m)$

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FIG 2

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RELATION BETWEEN
 λ AND $\text{LOG}_{10} \frac{kG^2}{r^2\Delta^2}$ FOR
VARIOUS METEOROLOGICAL
CONDITIONS.

PULSE LENGTH 1.5 μ s.

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S. 41500 F.

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FIG. 3

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VALUES OF n AND nX
FOR WATER AND ICE
FIG. 4.

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DATE 14 - 10 - 41

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RELATION BETWEEN
 λ AND $\text{LOG}_{10} \frac{RG^2}{r^2 \Delta^2}$ FOR
ICE PARTICLES AND HAIL

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S. 41 502 F.

FIG. 5

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RESEARCH
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RELATIVE REDUCTION OF
CLOUD ECHO INTENSITY
DUE TO ATTENUATION

$h = 0.5 \text{ KM.}$

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S. 41503 F.

RPT No. 7A31
INDEX No. CVO

FIG. 6.

DATE 14-10-41

ATTENUATION

**RESEARCH
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COMPANY, LTD.**

VALUES OF $\text{LOG}_{10} \sigma_{\text{KM}^{-1}}$ AND
OF THE db LOSS PER KM

DIAMETER OF WATER
DROPLETS LESS THAN 0.05CM.
FOGS, MIST AND STRATUS
CLOUDS

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S41504F.**

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FIG. 7.

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ATTENUATION
FIG. B.

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RPT. No. 7831
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DATE 14 - 10 - 41

$\text{LOG}_{10} \sigma_{\text{km}^{-1}}$

db LOSS
PER KM.

200.0
100.0
50.0
20.0
10.0
5.0
2.0
1.0
0.5
0.2
0.1
0.05
0.02
0.01

$M = 9.2 \text{ g PER CU. M.}$

$M = 0.83 \text{ g PER CU. M.}$

1 2 3 4 5 7 10 20 50 100 λ_{cm}

RESEARCH
LABORATORIES OF THE
GENERAL
ELECTRIC
COMPANY, LTD.

ATTENUATION OF INTENSITY
CAUSED BY WATER DROPLETS.
VALUES OF $\text{LOG}_{10} \sigma_{\text{KM}}$ AND
OF THE db LOSS PER KM.

DRAWING NO
S. 41506 F.

RPT NO. 7831
INDEX NO. CVD

FIG. 9.

DATE 14 - 10 - 41

